

METHODS OF USING THE METHOD OF COMMUNICATIVE TEACHING IN MASTERING MUSIC CULTURE

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the reforms in the field of education, art and culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the formation of musical culture in schoolchildren, the methods of teaching students through interactive methods, interactive education. .

Keywords: teacher, lesson, music, culture, art, performance, skill, direction, tradition, knowledge, demand, offer.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasi ta'lim, san'at va madaniyat sohasidagi islohotlar, musiqa madaniyatini maktab o'quvchilarida shakllantirish, interaktiv usullari orqali o'quvchilarni o'qitish, muloqotli ta'lim berishning metodlar haqida barafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qituvchi, dars, musiqa, madaniyat, san'at, ijro, mahorat, yo'nalish, an'ana, bilim, talab, taklif.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о реформах в сфере образования, искусства и культуры Республики Узбекистан, формировании музыкальной культуры у школьников, методах обучения школьников с помощью интерактивных методов, интерактивном обучении.

Ключевые слова: учитель, урок, музыка, культура, искусство, исполнение, мастерство, направление, традиция, знание, спрос, предложение.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and "Kokand" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 "On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts" Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 "Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3].Ensuring the development and prospects of the Republic of Uzbekistan depends on the changes taking place in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres, and in order to actively participate in such changes, high-level general and special knowledge, intellectual capacity, broad outlook and

skillful use of information communications are required. Based on these requirements, the training of pedagogic personnel is one of the most important tasks of today.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan noted: “Our great goals set before us today, our achievement of our good intentions, the renewal of our society, the progress and prospects of our lives, the reforms we are implementing, the results of our plans, the fate of all these, above all, meet the requirements of the time, we all realize that it is closely related to the problem of training highly qualified, conscious specialists”! Therefore, in the first stage of the implementation of the goals and objectives of the “National Personnel Training Program”, it was defined to organize the training of pedagogues and scientific pedagogues and their professional development at a level that meets the requirements of the time.

In the second stage, the technical and information base of educational institutions will be strengthened, the educational process will be provided with high-quality educational literature and advanced pedagogical technologies. In this sense, the implementation of advanced pedagogical technologies is also important. That is why it is one of the important requirements of today to further improve the teacher's professional skills, to organize the process of training pedagogical personnel based on a technological approach, and to prepare future teachers for this activity.

The technological approach to education is one of the factors that actively influence the pedagogical process and determine its effectiveness, integrity and success. Teaching through interactive methods and communicative teaching is a resource of standard teaching. As a result of using the method of teaching and working in small groups, it is possible to speed up the teaching process, that is, to raise the development potential to a high level, and create conditions for deep and extensive learning of the content of the training. Not all active learning methods are interactive. When we talk about interactive teaching methods, first of all, it is necessary to understand the method of studying and mastering the subject among students, which enhances the process of interaction and teaching from the point of psychological mechanism. Among them, the first example is working in small groups. There are many reasons why small group work methods are rarely used in today's teaching process, including the predominance of old-fashioned methods of explanation, demonstration and illustration, and new, innovative, communication-based methods. lack of confidence in teaching methods. In addition, teachers themselves do not know

about interactive teaching methods, the lack of methodological training is the reason why these methods are not widespread. In addition, today, the application of interactive teaching methods in medical universities is one of the urgent problems. Their correct application to the teaching process can raise the educational process to a higher level, and in the future, it is necessary to bring the teacher of general practice closer to the real life situation, in which he should acquire scientific thinking and professional skills based on the state standard.

Purpose and issues of interactive teaching methods.

The main essence of interactive teaching methods is that all students involved in the course of the lesson understand their own knowledge and thoughts while studying and mastering them through discussion. One of the main requirements is unity, joint thinking, and joint activities among students in the process of studying the curriculum, each student can share his opinion, innovation, knowledge and propose a solution to the problem. is done through .

The main issues of using the teaching process in the interactive mode at the department of general surgery are:

- raising the interest of students in the process of learning music;
- bringing the teaching process closer to the real conditions of the teacher's life;
- effective communication methods, proper formation of teacher-student and mutual communication skills;
- raising the process of mastering new theoretical knowledge and practical skills to a new level;
- increasing students' responsibility for the educational process. When using interactive methods, the student becomes the main member of the learning process of the group lesson, and his fundamental knowledge is considered the basis of the learning center. The teacher, in turn, does not give new, ready-made knowledge to students, but increases mastery among most students by developing the process of independent research and thinking. The difference between traditional teaching methods and interactive methods is the confrontation between the teacher and the student. changes the process: student activity prevails over the activity of the teacher, in turn, the main goal of the teacher is to create high-level conditions for the initiative thinking process of students. prepares necessary assignments, formulates questions and topics for communication among students, gives consultations, controls the process of implementation of time and planning stages.[4]

Interactive methods:

- increases students' interest;

- at the same time, the group actively involves all students in the lesson process;
- increases the result of using any reading materials;
- increases the efficiency of active learning of the curriculum;
- provides feedback;
- forms and increases the ratio of independent thought and knowledge among students;
- accelerates practical skills;
- improves interpersonal communication skills;
- causes a change in behavior. The main rules for organizing the interactive learning process:
- It is necessary to involve all students in the learning process.[5]

For this, it is necessary to use modernized technologies that involve all students in the learning process. - It is necessary to create conditions for the implementation of one's own opinion, to positively evaluate students who actively participate and have the right actions. - It is necessary to ensure the conditions of the educational auditorium in such a way that students can easily change their places and move to work in small and large groups. - Accurately link all treatments and timelines. It is necessary not to break the rules, having agreed on this at the beginning of the lesson.

For example: all students should be tolerant of all the speech and opinion of their peers, everyone should be able to speak freely and be respected.[6]

Mandatory conditions for the organization of interactive teaching methods:

- A reliable and positive relationship between the teacher and the student;
 - Mutual reflection during the discussion between the teacher and the student.
 - Including vivid examples and evidence in the educational process.
 - Multifaceted data, types of activities, their mobility.
 - Inclusion of external and internal motivation of activity and interest of students.

Preference of interactive teaching methods:

1. increase interest activity and motivation among students.
2. to increase the responsibility and independence of students in relation to the results of teaching activities.
3. Students acquire new knowledge and skills.
4. students' ability to acquire practical skills and be ready to use them.
5. forming a respectful attitude towards colleagues and others.

6. development of evidence-based communication methods.
7. fosters curiosity, creative mood and cooperative relations among students.
8. Makes the atmosphere of the lesson process positive for the teacher, maintains the ability to work and a good mood.
9. Effectiveness of evaluation of the results of the educational process by the teacher.
10. the use of interactive methods of teaching makes the educational process more controlled and durable, the teacher increases his confidence to manage the process and achieve the planned results by using his professional skills during the lesson.

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